

VALIDATION OF A VISUAL STYLE A PICTURE IS WORTH A THOUSAND WORDS, BUT WHAT ARE THE WORDS?

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ABSTRACT

This case study describes the process we follow to validate the perception of the Océ corporate user interface style, called OCEAN (Debije-Meessen and Jansen 2006). To validate the perception we look at three different qualities of the style: design quality, commercial quality and emotional quality. For these three different issues we choose dedicated test formats.

Keywords: Perception, Validation, Visual design, User Interface, Design quality.

INTRODUCTION

Our OCEAN products have been tested on usability issues on product- or system-level (Bouwmeester and den, Bosma, 2006). The perception of the style was always a secondary subject. So far no specific test has been conducted focusing on perception of the OCEAN style. After several years of developing OCEAN products it's time to validate the perception of the style. The validation process is still in progress.

By choosing a rather unorthodox format for the validation, we hope to create an open and pleasant atmosphere. An atmosphere that creates mental room for participants to formulate their opinion on style and to describe their personal experience. Previous validation moments taught us that it is not easy for people to talk about the emotional aspects of products or experiences.

GOAL

The goal of the validation of the perception of OCEAN is to establish the qualities of the OCEAN style.

The validation will expose the current state of design and check whether the intentions on perception of OCEAN have been achieved.

To validate the perception of the OCEAN style we will look at three different qualities. First of all, design qualities or *aesthetics*, secondly the commercial qualities or *added value* and third the emotional qualities or *user experience*.

METHOD

Because of the diverse nature of the qualities, each test phase will have its own approach and interpretation. In total, three phases will be conducted.

VALIDATION OF ESTHETICS

The first phase is to validate the design qualities of the style. We want to find out what the OCEAN style is according to Océ Designers.

Figure 1. Image result of the positioning of the OCEAN pictures.

Individual sessions

In the individual session we asked the designers to position OCEAN images along a virtual scale, running from 'the most', to 'the least' OCEAN. Next to this positioning we asked them to comment their choices and add applicable words derived from the Microsoft

Desirability Toolkit (Benedek and Miner, 2002) . The last exercise was to fill a SWOT analysis for the OCEAN style.

Common session

The outcome of the individual sessions were discussed in a common workshop. All individual SWOT's were combined in a common SWOT analysis and tension points were defined.

VALIDATION OF THE ADDED VALUE

The second phase is to validate the importance of OCEAN as a style on the Océ portfolio. To validate this added value a number of Océ colleagues were invited in groups¹.

Workshop: Have I got news for you

We've set up a workshop according the HIGNFY-format.² We interpreted the format in a way it would fit the needs and goal of this validation phase. We re-used the idea of teams and scoreboards.

Homework assignment

As a kind of preparation and sensitizing each of the participants were asked to select an example of good style and think what's good about it. The examples had to be sent in an email several days before the workshop. As start of the workshop we showed the examples and asked all participants to explain their choice(s).

Four OCEAN pictures "Odd one out round"

Four pictures shown, which one doesn't belong to this series keeping OCEAN in mind? Each team is asked to eliminate one of the pictures and explain why. Other teams could react and also add their opinion.

Figure 2. Example of a set of 4 OCEAN pictures.

Object round "Tabloid headlines round"

Two objects were handed over to each of the teams. They were asked to prepare a short presentation about each of the objects in order to explain what's OCEAN about it and what is not. Keywords were written down on a label.

The objects were selected based on the strengths and weaknesses of OCEAN according to the phase 1 test.

Figure 3. Three of the objects used in the object round.

Coming up next

As an experiment on the format, a video-conference workshop will be conducted. Members of two foreign R&D locations will compete as teams and the test will be conducted from Venlo, The Netherlands.

A wrap-up session will be planned. All participants will be invited to share their experiences and results will be presented. During this wrap-up session there will be room for a plenary discussion [4].

¹ Stompff, G. (1&3); Henze L.A.R. (2&3); Jong, F. de (1); Vliembergen E. van (1); Stappers P.J. (3); Smulders F.E.H.M. (3); Buijs J.A. (3). (1) Océ Technologies B.V., NL. (2) P5 consultants, NL (3) TU Delft, faculty of IDE, NL. (2011) User centred design in the wild. *International Conference on Engineering Design, ICED11. Conference proceedings*, 15 – 18 August, Technical University of Denmark, DK.

² 'Have I got news for you', Hat trick Productions for the BBC. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Have_I_Got_News_for_You

VALIDATION OF THE USER EXPERIENCE

The third phase of the test is to validate the user experience of the OCEAN style. This phase will be executed with (potential) users of OCEAN products. An attention point will be a global composition of the participants group. These tests are planned in Q2 of 2012.

WHAT WE'VE LEARNED

All the sessions gave us a lot of valuable insights. Not only on the actual perception of the style but also on the methods we used. The experiments we performed on the format of the sessions.

EXPERIENCES ON PHASE 1

The only substantive remark on phase 1 method is that the format is suitable for designers. The (design) language needed for the exercises is however less appropriate for non-designers.

This dedicated character makes the format highly usable for designers. They master the language and are given a stage to express their personal design opinion. By participating in this test, awareness is created throughout the design department. Next to this, it acts as a sensitizer for the common workshop.

The common workshop increases the awareness created in the individual session. It proves that it is valuable to share each others vision and to gain a shared understanding.

EXPERIENCES ON PHASE 2 (SO FAR)

The gaming format of this second phase created a pleasant atmosphere where people feel free to share their opinion and react in a spontaneous way.

Still it was a serious game. All participants were aware of the goal of the workshop and the need of their contribution. Sharing vision and creating a shared understand is a valuable exercise.

The limited opportunity for observation is a point of interest for future sessions. The current method is not very approachable for designers in the team who are used to observe usability test.

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